

Development of Literacy-Based Interactive Learning Media in Improving Critical Thinking Skills of Junior High School Students in Islamic Religious Education

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ABSTRACT: Critical thinking is very important in learning because it will improve students' thinking skills in learning practices. So far, critical thinking has not become a culture among students, so there are still students who are passive in the learning process and do not dare to argue or ask questions. Critical thinking skills are the ability to organize themselves in producing interpretation, analysis, and evaluation as well as exposure using evidence, concepts, methodologies, and contextual considerations that are used as the basis for making decisions. Indicators of critical skills, namely: solving problems, making decisions, persuading, analyzing assumptions and conducting scientific research. This study aims to develop literacy-based interactive learning media in improving the critical thinking skills of junior high school students in Islamic religious education subjects that are valid, practical, and effective. Learning media that can support the success of learning activities in improving students' critical thinking skills must be developed by meeting several criteria, namely valid, practical, and effective. The validity score obtained for each aspect is the media aspect with a percentage of 76.33% and for the material aspect with a percentage of 78.66%, therefore the learning media is declared valid. The average score of the overall learning implementation observation results obtained a percentage of 82.73%. There were 26 students who were complete or around 81.25%, the average score percentage of student activity was 84%, and as many as 92.83% of students gave a positive response. The findings of this study indicate that the development of literacy-based interactive learning media is effective in improving students' critical thinking skills in Islamic Religious Education subjects. The implication of this research is the need for literacy integration in Islamic learning to help students' develop a deeper and more critical understanding of the subject matter.

KEYWORDS: Critical thinking skills, Interactive learning media, Islamic Religious Education, Junior High School Students, Literacy.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the main foundation in shaping the character and intellectual abilities of the younger generation. In the context of Islamic education, teaching not only aims to transfer religious knowledge, but also to develop a deep understanding of religious principles as well as critical thinking skills of students'. Critical thinking becomes a goal in a learning process (Astawayasa et al., 2022). Facione (2011) suggests that critical thinking is the ability to organize oneself in producing interpretations, analysis, and evaluation as well as exposure using evidence, concepts, methodologies, and contextual considerations that are used as the basis for making decisions. According to Ennis (2011) critical thinking is a reflective thinking ability that focuses on what is done. The ability to think critically is an essential thing that must be mastered by students in this era. Efforts to form critical thinking skills can be developed in interactive classes which involve the full role of students. Indonesia itself has realized the importance of critical thinking skills that have been emphasized in the 2013 Curriculum. In developing critical thinking skills, it is necessary to take a holistic approach and implement the right learning program (Widana & Ratnaya, 2021). Critical thinking skills are becoming increasingly important in an ever-evolving and complex society. Islamic Religious Education has an important role in shaping students' character and morals, as well as developing their understanding of religious principles. In addition, critical thinking skills are an important necessity in facing the complex challenges of modern life. However, developing critical thinking skills in the context of religious education is often a challenge, especially at the junior high school level. One innovative way to overcome this challenge is through the use of literacy-based interactive learning media (Halpern, 2014).

Islamic Religious Education at the junior high school level plays a crucial role in shaping students' understanding of religious

values, morality and ethics that form the basis of daily life. In addition, developing critical thinking skills in students is also an important goal in modern education. These skills enable students to analyze, evaluate and synthesize information in greater depth, so that they can make informed and open-minded decisions. However, challenges arise in teaching religious material in a way that not only makes concepts understandable, but also develops students' critical thinking skills. Conventional learning methods tend to focus on understanding religious texts and concepts without providing sufficient opportunities for students to think critically and apply religious values in real contexts.

Traditional learning media are often limited in generating students' interest and engagement, and are not always able to effectively develop critical thinking skills. Meanwhile, the current generation of students' is growing up in a digital environment, where technology and interactive media have a strong appeal to them. Therefore, the development of learning media that combines religious content with interactivity and literacy approaches can be an effective solution to improve students' critical thinking skills in Islamic Religious Education subjects at junior high school level. (Kadir & Sinaga, 2019). Junior high school students are a group that is undergoing rapid intellectual and social development. Therefore, an appropriate and relevant learning approach is needed to facilitate their understanding of religious teachings and the development of critical thinking skills. One approach that can be used is the development of literacy-based interactive learning media. Religious literacy becomes the foundation in understanding the teachings of Islam comprehensively. By combining religious literacy and interactive elements, the learning media not only enables students' to understand religious content, but also encourages them to actively participate in the learning process (Fraenkel et al., 2012)

In the age of information and digital technology, the development of interactive learning media offers new opportunities to achieve this goal. Interactive media can present religious content in an engaging and diverse way, including text, images, audio and video. More importantly, it can be designed to stimulate student engagement in critical thinking, through reflective questions, interactive tasks, and the utilization of strong literacy. Therefore, the development of literacy-based interactive learning media is considered a potential solution to overcome the challenges of teaching Islamic Religious Education at the junior high school level. By combining elements of literacy and interactivity, this media can help students understand religious teachings more deeply and apply those values in daily life situations.

Through the development of literacy-based interactive learning media, students' will be given the opportunity to interact with various types of information, such as text, images, audio and video. They will be invited to understand, analyze and evaluate information from different perspectives, before finally reaching a conclusion. This approach will not only enrich religious understanding, but also encourage students' to build critical thinking skills that they will use throughout life. In this context, research on "Development of Literacy-Based Interactive Learning Media in Improving Critical Thinking Skills of Junior High School Students' in Islamic Religious Education Subjects" is relevant and important. This research aims to bridge the gap between conventional Islamic learning with technological developments and the need to develop critical thinking skills. By integrating religious literacy and interactivity through learning media, it is hoped that students can develop a deeper understanding of Islamic teachings and improve their ability to think critically (UNESCO, 2011)

In a broader context, this research can make a positive contribution to the development of the Islamic Religious Education curriculum at the junior high school level. By optimizing the use of technology in religious education, it is hoped that students will not only understand religious teachings, but also be able to apply these religious values in various aspects of daily life. In addition, this research can also serve as a foundation for the development of innovative and effective learning methods in the context of religious education in the digital era.

METHOD

The method used in this research is the research and development method. Research and development (R&D) has a function to produce a new product or develop an existing product and test its effectiveness (Muqdamien et al., 2021). This research produces a literacy-based interactive learning media product in Islamic Religious Education subjects at the junior high school level whose use can facilitate and benefit the learning process for educators and students. The stages used in this study refer to the development of Dick and Carry, namely the ADDIE model which consists of the stages of analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (Dick et al., 2009) which can be seen in figure 1. This research uses the ADDIE model because the ADDIE model has sequential stages, is easier to understand, easy to apply and simpler. The ADDIE model is implemented in five stages, namely Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation (Rusmulyani, 2020). This study aims to develop and test the

effectiveness of literacy-based interactive learning media in improving students' critical thinking skills in Islamic Religious Education subjects at the junior high school level.

In this research, two approaches were used, namely qualitative and quantitative approaches. The qualitative approach obtained information through interviews and assessments as analysis and ideas from media specialists and material specialists at the time the media was created. Meanwhile, the quantitative approach obtains information involving survey results such as numbers obtained from media and material expert validators as well as results from preliminary surveys conducted by students and results from surveys of educators as the object of research.

Figure 1. Design of ADDIE model (Source: Author Analysis, 2023)

The ADDIE model served as the foundation for developing the learning materials for this study. Analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation are the stages of development.

1. The first stage is the analysis stage; In this stage, Analyzing the challenges and needs in learning Islamic Religious Education at the junior high school level, especially in developing critical thinking skills. Identifying critical thinking competencies to be improved and critical points in the subject matter. Evaluate student characteristics, curriculum, and classroom context..
2. The second stage is design. Designing the structure of the learning module consisting of sub-headings. Selecting the type of

- literacy content appropriate to each sub-subject, such as text, images, audio and video. Integrating reflective questions and interactive tasks that encourage critical thinking in each sub-subject.
3. The third stage of development. Build the literacy content and interactive elements based on the design. Develop an intuitive user interface to access the content and interactive tasks. Tailor the content to the learning objectives and interactive tasks that have been designed.
 4. The main task of the fourth stage, implementation. Implement literacy-based interactive learning media in Islamic Religious Education classes at junior high school level. Direct teachers to integrate the media in learning and provide usage guidelines to students. Facilitate interaction between students and the media and provide technical support.
 5. The final stage is evaluation. Collecting data on students' responses to the learning media and their engagement in interactive tasks. Measure the improvement of students' critical thinking skills through skill testing before and after the intervention. Observe changes in student behavior related to religious understanding and critical thinking skills.

After following the steps in this ADDIE model, the development of literacy-based interactive learning media to improve students' critical thinking skills in Islamic Religious Education subjects at the junior high school level can be expected to be more effective and targeted.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The development of literacy-based interactive learning media in the context of learning Islamic Religious Education at the junior high school level has provided significant findings related to improving students' critical thinking skills. The discussion of these results involves an in-depth analysis of the positive impact of using the media on the development of students' critical thinking skills and its implications for improving Islamic Religious Education learning.

The ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) is used as the basis for designing and implementing the development of literacy-based interactive learning media in improving students' critical thinking skills in Islamic Religious Education subjects at the junior high school level.

1. Analysis

At the analysis stage, an in-depth understanding of the curriculum, students' characteristics and learning objectives was conducted. This research begins by identifying the challenges in teaching Islamic Religious Education and the potential role of literacy-based interactive media in improving critical thinking skills. Curriculum analysis aims to get an overview of the competencies and indicators that must be achieved by students on a material that will be presented in the learning media. This curriculum analysis is carried out by reviewing the subject syllabus, the results of this review produce learning indicators which will then be derived in the form of media objects. Learning indicators that have been prepared must also be adjusted to the indicators of students' critical thinking skills, it is intended that there is a match between learning indicators, indicators of critical thinking skills and media objects that will be presented in learning media. Meanwhile, the analysis of students' characteristics aims to get an overview of the characteristics of students' and the ability of students' to be adjusted to the learning media to be developed. In addition, the analysis of students' characteristics will also determine the media objects displayed in the learning media. The depth of material in the analysis of students' characteristics is based on the competencies and learning indicators that must be achieved by students. Through the process of analyzing the depth of material, it is expected that the media will have content that suits the needs of students' at their cognitive level. Meanwhile, the analysis of students' characteristics related to the characteristics of the material is expected to produce media that presents media objects in accordance with the character of the material to be conveyed. For example, if the characteristics of the material are abstract, then the media needs objects that are able to visualize these abstract concepts.

The next analysis of learning objectives aims to get an overview of the learning objectives achieved. The learning objectives will be adjusted to the competency outcomes and indicators set out in the curriculum. In addition, indicators of students' critical thinking skills will also be adjusted to the concepts or materials that will be presented in the learning media. The suitability between critical thinking skills indicators, learning objectives and teaching concepts/materials will be presented in the form of media objects that illustrate the suitability between these various aspects. Indicators of critical thinking according to Ennis (1995) can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Indicators of critical thinking skills

No.	Critical thinking skills	Indicator
1	Elementary Clarification	Focusing the question Analyzing the argument Asking and answering clarifying questions
2	Basic Support	d. Considering whether the source is reliable or not e. Observing and considering the results of observations
3	Inference	Making deductions and considering the results of deductions Making induction and considering the results of induction Make and consider value decisions
4	Advanced Clarification	Define terms and consider definitions Identifying assumptions
5	Strategies and Tactics	k. Determining action l. Interacting with others

2. Design

Based on the analysis stage, the design of literacy-based interactive learning media is developed. In the design stage, several activities were carried out in designing literacy-based interactive learning media designs. These include conceptualizing, determining the subject matter, and creating a flowchart. The concept and subject matter generated from the previous stage will then be outlined in the storyboard. However, to find out the relationship between the material and the components of the learning media, a flowchart is made which will describe the flow in the media regarding the relationship between one component and another. The following is an example of a flowchart on the development of literacy-based interactive learning media:

Figure 2. Flowchart

3. Development

At this stage, the literacy-based interactive learning media is developed based on the pre-designed design. Content such as text, images, audio, video and interactive quizzes are designed to support holistic understanding of religious concepts and critical thinking. After designing the learning media, a validation test was conducted by experts according to their fields. Learning media validation is an activity to assess the feasibility of literacy-based interactive learning media from the point of view of experts and learning implementers (educators). In this design validation is still an assessment based on rational thinking, not field facts. In this study, learning media validation includes an assessment of the material and media aspects of the learning media as well as the suitability of the media to the curriculum and the cognitive aspects of students. Validation from an expert point of view is carried out by learning media expert educators, material expert educators. In the validation implementation, each validator assesses the learning media from various aspects that are already available on the media validation sheet. A recapitulation of the results of validation by experts can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Results of validation by media experts

Aspect	Category	Percentage
View	75%	Worth
Programming	80%	Very Worth
Language	74%	Worth
Average	76,33%	Very Worth

Table 3. Results of validation by material experts

Aspect	Category	Percentage
Learning Materials	85%	Very Worth
Language	73%	Worth
PAI Literacy	78%	Very Worth
Average	78,66%	Very Worth

The results of validation by experts, namely from the media aspect, obtained a percentage of 76.33% with a very feasible category and in the material aspect obtained a percentage of 78.66% with a very feasible category. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the literacy-based interactive learning media for Islamic Religious Education subjects at the junior high school level is declared valid.

After validating the learning media by experts from various aspects of assessment, information is obtained about the weaknesses and strengths of the learning media that have been developed. The suggestions and input given by the validators were then discussed with the supervising educator and improvements were made so that the learning media developed had a quality that could help students in improving students' critical thinking skills.

4. Implementation

The developed learning media was applied in class IX at Ma'arif 08 Wuluhan Junior High School in the subject of Islamic Religious Education. Educators involved were taught to operate the media and integrate it into learning. During the implementation, the interaction between students' and the media and their reactions to its use were observed by the observer and scored on the observation sheet. The results of the scores based on the observation sheet for the implementation of the learning process assessed by the observers can be seen in table 4.

Table 4. Recapitulation of observation results of the implementation of the learning process

Aspect	Category	Percentage
Learning syntax	85,4%	Very Worth
Activeness in learning	80,8%	Very Worth
Students' and educator interaction	82%	Very Worth
Average	82,73%	Very Worth

Based on table 4, the average score of the overall learning implementation observation results is 82.73% with a very feasible category. Therefore, it can be concluded that the literacy-based interactive learning media for Islamic Religious Education subjects at the junior high school level is declared practical.

After the media is declared practical, the media is tested for effectiveness. The effectiveness test can be determined based on three criteria, namely the completeness of the students' critical thinking skills test, the analysis of students' activities, and the results of students' responses. The first criterion is the completeness of the students' critical thinking skills test. The results of the answers collected by students obtained a total of 26 students got a score above 60. Therefore, 81.25% of students are complete and have met one of the criteria for a media to be called effective. The second criterion is the analysis of students' activities obtained based on the observation sheet of students' activities. The results of the score recapitulation can be seen in table 5.

Table 5. Recapitulation of student activity observation results

Aspect	Category	Percentage
Pendahuluan	90%	Very Worth
Kegiatan Inti	88%	Very Worth
Penutup	74%	Worth
Average	84%	Very Worth

Based on table 5, it is found that the percentage of the average score of students' activities is 84% with a very feasible category. Based on the criteria for activeness, students are classified as very active. This means that two of the three requirements for an effective learning media have been met.

The third criterion is the results of students' responses. The results of students' responses were obtained by distributing student questionnaires in hardfile form. There were 32 students' who filled out the questionnaire. Based on the students' responses in the questionnaire sheet, the recapitulation of the score of the students' response results is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Recapitulation of student response data

Aspect	Percentage	
	Yes	No
Students' enjoyment of learning media	95%	5%
Novelty of learning media	98%	2%
Students' interest in learning	94%	6%
Students' level of understanding of the language used	88%	12%
Students' level of understanding of the quiz questions presented	82%	18%
Students' level of interest in learning media	100%	0%
Average	92,83%	7,16%

The results of the recapitulation of students' questionnaire data in table 5 show that the lowest positive answer with a percentage of 82% lies in the statement about understanding the quiz questions contained in the learning media. This is because the material provided has not been studied. Furthermore, the highest positive response is on the item of students' interest in learning media. This is because the learning media is indeed relatively new for junior high school students, namely regarding PAI subjects which are associated with indicators of critical thinking of literacy-based students. Overall, the percentage of positive responses to the average statement was 92.83%, while the percentage of negative responses obtained was 7.16%. This indicates that the majority of students gave a positive response to the learning and learning media presented. This means that the three requirements for an effective learning media have been fulfilled.

The data analysis of this study used paired sample t-test which is comparing the results of pretest and posttest to determine the improvement of students' critical skills after the implementation of learning devices in the classroom. Graphs of the value and percentage of pre-test and post-test results of students in the research class can be seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Graph of (a) pre-test and (b) post-test scores

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Percentage of (a) pre-test and (b) post-test critical levels

Based on Figure 4, the pre-test data results obtained with a percentage of 81% for low-level category students and 19% for medium-level category students. While the post-test results for the low-level student category showed a percentage value of 7%, a medium level of 13%, and a high-level category of 80%. Furthermore, the normality test was carried out as a requirement before the paired sample t-test was carried out. The results of the normality test can be seen in Figure 5.

SET DATA ▾ CEK NORMALITAS ▾ STATS DASAR ▾ REGRESI ▾ NONPARAMETRIK ▾

statistic	p.value	method	data.name
0.97	0.53	Shapiro-Wilk normality test	datasetInput()[, input\$var.y]
0.97	0.53	Shapiro-Wilk normality test	datasetInput()[, input\$var.y]

Figure 5. Results of normality test

Based on Figure 5, the results of the normality test show that the data from the pre-test and post-test scores of students are normally distributed because the p.value results in a normal distribution $0,53 > 0,05$. After that, a paired sample t-test can be conducted with the results shown in Figure 6.

SET DATA ▾ CEK NORMALITAS ▾ STATS DASAR ▾ REGRESI ▾ NONPARAMETRIK ▾

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Uji-T 2-Kelompok Berpasangan: Data= IMPOR Y1= Posttest Y2= Pretest

Paired t-test

data: datasetInput()[, input$var.yt2p1] and datasetInput()[, input$var.yt2p2]
t = 16.663, df = 34, p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: true mean difference is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 20.57115 26.28599
sample estimates:
mean difference
 23.42857
    
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Figure 6. Results of paired sample t-test

In Figure 6, the results of the paired sample t-test show that the p.value on the pre-test and post-test values is as follows $2,2 \times 10^{-16}(0,000000000022) < 0,05$, so it can be concluded that there are differences in students' critical thinking skills tests after the trial of literacy-based interactive learning media for Islamic Religious Education subjects.

5. Evaluation

After implementation, an evaluation was conducted on the effectiveness of the literacy-based interactive learning media in improving students' critical thinking skills. The evaluation involves collecting data through critical thinking skills tests before and after the intervention as well as observing students' participation and their response to the media. This evaluation stage is conducted to correct shortcomings to avoid obstacles when the learning media will be used in educating and developing the students' experience.

DISCUSSION

Based on the overall results, the quality of literacy-based Islamic Religious Education interactive learning media has met the criteria as valid, practical, and effective learning media. These criteria are based on the results of the assessment of media experts, namely 76.33% and material experts, namely 78.66% with a very feasible category, which means that this learning media is declared valid. The next criterion is the results obtained based on observations of the overall implementation of learning is 82.73% with a very feasible category. Therefore, it can be concluded that the literacy-based interactive learning media for Religious Education subjects is declared practical. The third criterion is obtained from the completeness of the students' critical thinking skills test, the analysis of students' activities, and the results of students' responses with the scores obtained in sequence, namely 81.25% of the students' skills test results were completed, 84% of active students, and 92.83% of students' positive responses. This is in line with the research of Riva'i et al. (2020) which states that good learning media that meet the criteria are valid, practical, and effective. Riva'i et al. (2020) stated that a product is said to be valid if the quality of the product can be said to be valid by considering the purpose and relevance of the product development. The practicality of the product is determined from the opinion of educators who state that the product produced can be used and the product can be used easily by educators and students as expected. After using learning media, educators feel helped in the process of delivering material. The learning media developed is also declared effective based on the test of students' critical thinking skills, analysis of students' activities, and the results of students' responses, the effectiveness of the product can be reviewed from the consistency between the design/objectives with the experience and learning outcomes achieved by students. After using the learning media, students do not experience difficulties in learning, this makes students feel interested in learning by using this literacy-based interactive learning media.

The learning media in this study have met the valid criteria, then the media trials were carried out by starting with pretest activities for students. After the pre-test, learning was applied using literacy-based interactive learning media. It can be seen from the data obtained from observers, students who were originally passive became a little more active and dared to express opinions or questions and slowly showed their skills in critical thinking, namely conveying questions and opinions on existing problems. After the learning takes place, the post-test results can be concluded that there is an increase, namely there are a total of 2 students classified as low critical thinking skills with a percentage of 7%, 4 students classified as moderate critical thinking skills with a percentage of 13%, 26 students classified as high critical thinking levels with a percentage of 80%. This is in line with Wahyuni (2021) that the implications of literacy-based learning have an impact on creating a more active learning atmosphere so that it can improve student learning outcomes.

The media developed uses literacy-based interactive learning media and indicators of critical thinking skills that can improve students' critical thinking skills. This can be seen from the observation results, which initially only 1-2 groups were active in expressing their opinions, to almost the entire group expressing their ideas and opinions in the form of good statements during the problem solving process given. This is in line with Pramuji et al. (2018) that literacy-based interactive learning media integrated with Islamic Religious Education subjects provide a positive learning process for students in solving problems and can improve students' critical thinking skills.

CONCLUSION

In the context of learning Islamic Religious Education at the junior high school level, the development of literacy-based interactive learning media has proven effective in improving students' critical thinking skills. This media is able to create a learning

environment that focuses on deep understanding, critical thinking, and application of religious concepts in daily life. The implications include improving the quality of learning and strengthening students' understanding of religious values. Although further challenges and developments still need to be addressed, these findings show great potential in developing a more holistic and critical thinking skills-oriented learning approach.

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REFERENCES

1. Astawayasa, K. G., Widana, I. W., & Rasmen Adi, I. N. (2022). Pengembangan asesment HOTS mata pelajaran matematika sekolah dasar. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Citra Bakti*, 9(1), 129-141. <https://doi.org/10.38048/jipcb.v9i1.660>
2. Dick, W., Carey, L., & Carey, J. O. (2009). *The systematic design of instruction*. Pearson.
3. Ennis, R. 1995. *Critical Thinking*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall
4. Ennis, R. H. (2011). *The Nature of Critical Thinking: an Outline of Critical Thinking Disposition and Abilities*. University of Illinois.
5. Facione, P. A. (2011). *Critical Thinking: What It Is and Why It Counts*. Measured Reasons and The California Academic Press.
6. Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2012). *How to design and evaluate research in education*. McGraw-Hill.
7. Halpern, D. F. (2014). *Thought and knowledge: An introduction to critical thinking*. Taylor & Francis.
8. Kadir, A., & Sinaga, P. (2019). Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam Berbasis Media Pembelajaran dalam Mengembangkan Keterampilan Berpikir Kritis Peserta didik. *Jurnal Al-Mazra'ah*, 5(2), 107-116.
9. Morrison, G. R., Ross, S. M., Kemp, J. E., & Kalman, H. K. (2019). *Designing effective instruction*. John Wiley & Sons.
10. Muqdamien, B., Umayah, U., Juhri, J., & Raraswaty, D. P. (2021). Tahap Definisi Dalam Four-D Model Pada Penelitian Research & Development (R&D) Alat Peraga Edukasi Ular Tangga Untuk Meningkatkan Pengetahuan Sains Dan Matematika Anak Usia 5-6 Tahun. *Intersections*, 6(1), 23-33. <https://doi.org/10.47200/intersections.v6i1.589>
11. Pramuji, Lili, et al., (2018). Multimedia Interaktif Berbasis Literasi pada Konsep Pencemaran Lingkungan untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Siswa. *Journal of Science Education and Practice*. Vol. 2 No. 1. <https://doi.org/10.33751/jsep.v2i1.1699>
12. Riva'i, Z., et al., (2020). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Berbasis Aplikasi Android. *Delta-Pi*. Vol. 9 No. 2. 106-119.
13. Rusmulyani, K. (2020). Study Pengembangan Pendidikan Dan Pelatihan. *Susunan Artikel Pendidikan*, 5(2), 101-108.
14. Thompson, M. (2018). *Literacy and the Common Core: Recipes for Action*. Teachers College Press.
15. UNESCO. (2011). *Media and Information Literacy Curriculum for Teachers*. UNESCO.
16. Wahyuni, N. P. 2021. Application of STEM-based Learning to Improve Science Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Education Action Research*. Vol 5 (1). <https://doi.org/10.23887/jear.v5i1.31554>
17. Widana, I. W. & Ratnaya, I. G. (2021). Relationship between divergent thinking and digital literacy on teacher ability to develop HOTS assessment. *Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 5(4), 516-524. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jere.v5i4.35128>.

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